

**THE IMPACT OF ENGLISH ON THE
ALBANIAN TERMINOLOGY OF
BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION**

Linguistics

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Abstract

English has an impact in many European languages and Albanian language as well. English words have flooded everywhere and even unnecessary words are borrowed, so it has conquered several languages of the world. This spread of English words in the Albanian language lexicon of economics and business administration is a consequence of political, economic, cultural, scientific influence, etc., in particular after 1990 (in Albania, on the occasion of opening up to the world) and in Kosovo after June 1999 (on the occasion of the entry of NATO ground forces into Kosovo). English words or of English descent have entered as terms in particular areas of social activity. In the field of business administration, economics, finance, trade and management, these are terms that primarily denote notions and phenomena of international economics, financial and trade relations, US and UK monetary units, such as: arbitrage, audit, assets, balance sheet, business, businessman, board, budget, check, economy, export, fiscal, grant, import, equity, clearing, license, leader, trust, dollar, pound, sterling, etc.

Introduction

English is official/state language in US, Britain, Australia, New Zealand, Canada (beside French) and South Africa, as well as a state or official language in some other African countries. English also occupies a place in the political, economic and cultural life of India and Pakistan. It is also often used as a language of commerce, science and publicity in Africa, Asia and South America.

Certainly, borrowing differs from many social, political, economic and technical-technological circumstances. A country with a high level of education and culture borrows less from any other language. While an underdeveloped country in field of higher education, it is much more likely to borrow words and terms from another language of a more developed nation. Once many European and other languages borrowed from French which had political as well as economic status, from which the Russian borrowed also. While today it is borrowed in almost all languages from English, due to the great influence of England and the USA. Their great achievements, in general, in science, technology and economics, have led many Anglicism's to be incorporated into the lexicon of many languages, and also into the Albanian language.

The Value of the Term as a Special Lexicon Unit in Business Administration

Terms are the basic units of the specialized language lexicon, in this case also the business administration, which are distinguished and identified as such by other non-terminology units in accordance with those essential features that characterize and constitute the basis of the independent terminological lexicon as a separate subsystem in the standard Albanian language lexicon. The term for terminology thus emerges as the concentrated expression of a series of properties and features whose invention in the very content and essence of the term allows us to delve deeper into the phenomena of terminology, to understand its links to the system of concepts of the relevant field of knowledge, to find fairer solutions in the practice of terminological work, in the work of reflecting terms in the terminology dictionaries of economics-business administration, as well as in non-terminological ones.

A complete treatment of the relationship between word and meaning (lexical) is found in the work of J. Thomai "*Prejardhja semantike në gjuhën shqipe*" [19. Pp. 75-92]. In the context of these relationships the term problem is addressed also. Important in these relationships is the *concept problem expressed by the term and the lexical meaning problem denoted by the word*, although in the general sense the concept is expressed both *by the word (by those words denoting concepts) and by the term*. In the linguistic aspect, the explanation of the essence of the concept expressed by the term in relation to the term itself and the object (referent) can be done in breadth and depth, just as the lexical meaning of the word can be explained in relation to the word and object itself. Concerning the meaning of the word J. Thomai notes "*without these three links and without their close connection there can be no explanation of the word itself*" [19. P.76]. Looking at the lexical meaning even within the context of the concept he concludes that "any notion (concept) [2. P.39] and lexical meaning are two distinct planes, notion (= concept) is a logical category, lexical meaning is an organic element of language structure); notion (= concept) always remains the basis of the meaning, of the lexical content of the word" [19. P.77]. Within these relationships J. Thomai also addresses the problem of the term. For this he explains: "*For some word classes, notion*" (= concept) seems as "*direct content*", thus, one with lexical meaning. It is here especially for the terms in which the lexical meaning appears as "*description of the notion*" (= concept), because such a thing is requirement of terms themselves. In this case, we would see lexical meaning as the ability of the term (definitely linguistic) to mark a particular notion (= concept).

It follows from the above that while lexical meaning is important for the word (because all words have lexical meaning) and the concept ("the notion remains the basis of lexical meaning"), for the term the concept is essential. The lexical meaning of the terms, as it were, equates to the concept; [2. P.40] the concept thus emerges for the term as its sole content.

Transition in Albania and Kosovo

Before the start of the transition (in Albania, since 1990) and in Kosovo (since 1999), elements of foreign languages, including English, were introduced into Albanian mainly by cultural or indirect borrowings. Therefore, their numbers and density were much smaller.

With the opening of Albania to the world and with the arrival of UNMIK, KFOR, OSCE Mission in Kosovo, employees began to use English words, whether spoken or in writing; therefore changed the way of direct borrowing. This was because the contact between these two languages became direct.

Phrase Terms in Business Administration

The fond of *phrase terms*, that *name* new *details* of *notions* with which was enriched the terminology of business administration, especially after 1990 (in Albania) and after 1999 (in Kosovo) [17], like:

1. **arbitrazh (arbitration):** *arbitrazh i bursës* (arbitrage business (in stock market), *arbitrazh detar* (maritime arbitration), *arbitrazh i kurseve valutore* (arbitration of exchange (rates), *arbitrazh ndërkombëtar* (international arbitration), *arbitrazh i tregtisë ndërkombëtare* (international commercial arbitration), *arbitrazh pa rrezik* (risk less arbitrage), *arbitrazh tatimor* (tax arbitrage), *arbitrazh valutor* (currency arbitrage) etc.

2. **asete (A: aktive, K: pasuri, mjete) (gjëra me burime në pronësi të firmës që përdoren për mirëvajtje të biznesit) (assets):** *asete afatgjata* (non-current assets), *asete individuale* (individual assets), *asete jashtëbilancore* (off-balance sheet assets), *asete jo-financiare* (non-financial assets), *asete monetare* (monetary assets), *asete neto* (net assets), *asete sigurimi* (insurance assets), *asete të korporates* (corporate assets), *asete themelore* (underlying assets) etc.

3. **auditim (audit):** *auditim i bankës* (bank audit), *auditim i brendshëm* (internal audit), *auditim i jashtëm* (external audit), *auditim i vazhdueshëm* (continuous audit), *auditim operacional* (operational audit), *auditim procedural* (procedural audit) etc.

4. **bankë (bank):** *bankë arkëtimi* (collecting bank), *bankë e depozitave* (deposit bank), *bankë hipotekare* (mortgage bank), *bankë kombëtare* (national bank), *bankë komerciale* (commercial bank), *bankë kreditimi* (credit bank), *bankë qendrore* (central bank), *bankë shtetërore* (state bank), *bankë zhvillimi* (development bank) etc.

5. **bilanc (balance, sheet):** *bilanc bankar* (bank balance sheet), *bilanc i pagesave* (balance of payments), *bilanc i tregtisë së jashtme* (foreign trade balance), *bilanc tregtar* (trade balance), *bilanc vjetor* (annual balance) etc.

6. **çek (cheque (check, US))**: *çek i bardhë (blank check)*, *çek i diskutueshëm (negotiable check)*, *çek i garantuar (nga banka) (cashier's (official) check)*, *çek i limituar (limited check)*, *çek i shuar (i anuluar) (cancelled check)*, *çek i vërtetuar (K: konfirmuar) nga banka (certified check) etc.*

7. **deklaratë** (declaration): *deklaratë doganore (customs declaration)*, *deklaratë e furnizuesit (suppliers declaration)*, *deklaratë e përbashkët (joint declaration)*, *deklaratë importi (import declaration) etc.*

8. **ekonomi (economy)**: *ekonomi botërore (world economy)*, *ekonomi e komanduar (command economy)*, *ekonomi e tregut (market economy)*, *ekonomi kombëtare (national economy)*, *ekonomi tregu (market-driven economy)*, *ekonomi vendore (domestic economy) etc.*

9. **eksport** (export): *eksport i kapitalit (export of capital)*, *eksport i lejuar (approved export) etc.*

10. **import (import)**: *import i lejuar (approved import)*, *import i përkohshëm (temporary import)*, *import kapitali (import of capital)*, *import përfundimtar (definitive import) etc.*

11. **kapital (capital)**: *kapital aksionar (share capital)*, *kapital bazë (core capital)*, *kapital financiar (financial capital)*, *kapital i bankës (bank capital, funds)*, *kapital i deklaruar (stated capital)*, *kapital i kompanisë (company capital)*, *kapital kombëtar (capital stock of nation)*, *kapital qarkullues (circulating capital) etc.*

Conclusion

In some cases, determining the origin of English terms in business administration is difficult, even impossible, because, among other things, we have neither historical dictionary of Albanian language nor studies of lexical history in Albanian.

By comparing the lexical meaning, which constitutes the most essential part of the word and with the concept, which constitutes the most important side of the term, we discover that basic feature underlying the division of the boundary between the word and the term. For this reason, being fully associated with the concept, the term relates more closely, more directly to the object (referent) it expresses and in particular, to its most essential features.

To decide what to do with a foreign language element, in this case Anglicism's in business administration, it is no easy task. This should not even be the duty of a person, whatever his or her authority in this field is. Institutional work always would be the best choice, like in many other fields of knowledge, and for Anglicism's in business administration and economics.

To do this work it is required a considerable time, intensive and continuous work. In addition, a good deal of experience is required in dealing with borrowings in the past, both within our language and in other languages. Also, there is a need for sufficient knowledge and great

responsibility in this highly sensitive work and that seems to be missing and we are not acting adequately to the problem we are facing.

The penetration of foreign words into the Albanian language, in this case of Anglicism's in business administration, in this period of globalization, is very impetuous and it seems as if the defenders of the Albanian language are not able to confront such a large number of them.

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